

Greener Journal of Microbiology and Antimicrobials

ISSN: 2354-2284

Submission Date: 21/05/014

Accepted: 30/06/014

Published: 08/07/014

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Review Article

Mycotoxins in Stored Agricultural Products: Implications to Food Safety and Health and Prospects of Plant-derived Pesticides as Novel Approach to their Management

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ABSTRACT

Mycotoxins are toxic secondary metabolites from some species of *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium* *Penicillium* and their related fungi. Their contamination results generally in inferior quality of produce and produce end-products, food safety and ultimately barriers trans-border marketability of agro-produce. Though the presence of mycotoxigenic fungus on produce does not always translate to presence of mycotoxins; however, mycotoxins are silent killers and their effects could be submerged over a long period of time especially during intermittent exposures. These fungal toxins when ingested or inhaled participate in several metabolic dysfunctions in human and livestock systems such as immunological imbalance, cancers, allergies, abortions and in some cases death of the affected hosts. Conditions of high temperatures and relative humidity coupled with poor store standards and hygiene which characterized tropical subsistence farmsteads encourage mouldiness and mycotoxin contamination of agricultural products. The mycotoxins of most agricultural importance (aflatoxins, fumonisins, ochratoxins, trichothecenes) were enumerated in this review while their management strategies were also highlighted; with emphasis on plant-derived anti-mycotoxigenic interventions useable in low-input agricultural production systems of sub-Saharan Africa.

Keywords: Mycotoxins, plant-derived fungicides, *Aspergillus spp.*, *Fusarium spp.*, *Penicillium spp.*, trichothecenes.

INTRODUCTION

Mycotoxins are secondary metabolites produced by filamentous fungi on food crops that are capable of causing toxic responses such as diseases or death in humans and other animals when ingested depending on the level and duration of exposure (Bennett and Klich, 2003; Bandyopadhyay et al., 2007; Viljoen, 2013). Exposure could also be through skin contact or by inhalation of the spores-borne toxins. They are odourless, tasteless and colourless to the naked eye (Fapohunda, 2013; 2014). These poisonous chemical compounds are capable of causing acute or chronic effects on humans including the induction of cancer, birth defects, digestive systems disorders, reproductive dysfunction, immune suppression, impediment of liver metabolism, liver cirrhosis and premature puberty in girls (FAO, 2013; Viljoen, 2013). For example palutin (4-H-furo {3,2c} pyran-2(6H)-one) from *Penicillium griseofulvum*, and *P. expansum* commonly detected in apples and apple-based products can affect both plant and animal systems. This mycotoxin is reported to damage gastrointestinal tracts, respiratory systems, DNA and sulphhydryl bonds in many enzymes in humans (Reddy et al., 2010a). Synergy of mycotoxins in exacerbating some disease conditions such as kwashiorkor, malaria, HIV/AIDS and hepatocellular carcinoma has been suggested (Wagacha and Muthomi, 2008). Their prevalence and concentration are sporadic and vary annually even in the same location. Local weather patterns, crop damage and agronomic practices affect their production (Iowa State University, 2014). According to statistics up to 25% of the world's crops are mycotoxin-contaminated and over 4.5-5.0 billion people around the world especially in less developed nations are at the risk of chronic exposure to mycotoxins (Bryden, 2007; Bhat, 2008; Tiffany, 2013; Whitlow and Hagler, 2013). Though the risk is major, it is unappreciated by those residing in these third world countries as reported by Bandyopadhyay et al. (2007). A survey conducted on maize in Southeast Nigeria indicated that 80% of samples from different locations in the area were aflatoxin contaminated (Aja-Nwachukwu and Emejuaiwe, 2006); while that on street vended corn and groundnut-based snacks in Lagos showed 36% contamination with total aflatoxins exceeding permissible limits for the country (Ezekiel et al., 2012). Similar experiment in Thailand showed that

92% of commercial animal feed samples evaluated in that country were mycotoxin contaminated (Thanaboripat, 2011).

Viljoen (2013) reported that fighting fusarium head blight (FHB) of wheat and barley costs USD 2.6 billion while mycotoxins impress additional economic burden of USD1 billion dollars on the US economy annually. Furthermore, mycotoxins noted this source, are possible bio-terrorism weapons of mass destruction.

Mycotoxin producing fungi are ubiquitous (Murphy et al., 2006) and can infect grains at all levels from production to processing and the supply chains. A significant level of grain-mould infection occur in the field being encouraged by damp conditions at time of harvest, insect infestations, delayed harvesting as well as improper post-harvest handling, transporting, drying and storage (Reddy et al., 2013; Tiffany, 2013).

Mycotoxins are commonly associated with oil seeds, groundnut, spices, cotton seeds, soybean, cowpea and various tree nuts as well as several cereals like maize, wheat, barley, sorghum, oats and rye which serve as main staple for humans and raw materials for livestock (Farag, 2008; Tiffany, 2013). In addition they are found in milk, meat, coffee, wines, beers and eggs (Okello et al., 2010). Generally, 20 ppb is the allowed maximum limit of total aflatoxins in food meant for human consumption in most countries including the USA, Nigeria and UAE and as low as 4 ppb in the EU nations (Tiffany, 2013). Species of *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium* and *Penicillium* have been implicated in mycotoxins contamination of foods and feeds. *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* which require low water activity to grow are regarded as storage fungi while *Fusarium spp.* which requires high water tension is considered as field fungi (Whitlow and Hagler, 2013). Up to 300 mycotoxins have been identified; however, the agriculturally important ones are aflatoxins, fumonisins, ochratoxin A, zearalenone and the trichothecenes – nivanenol (NIV), deoxynivanenol (DON), diacetoxyscirpenol (DAS) and T-2 toxins (Bankole and Adebajo, 2003).

Preventive agronomic practices are recommended for control of mould growth and mycotoxin build-up on agro-produce, but may not be effective in all instances. Synthetic chemicals are handy in such cases to effect controls but have not been found very effective against mycotoxins (Okello et al., 2010). Again their use in plant protection are being de-emphasized due to mammalian toxicity and stimulation of resistance in pathogens stemming from their inappropriate or excessive applications (Tripathi and Dubey, 2004; Enyiukwu et al., 2014a). These twin problems and many such drawbacks reported in literature necessitated search for alternatives such as biological control and plant-based pesticides. Plant-derived pesticides are compatible with organic and conventional farming systems but are most suitable for low-input growers constituting the bulk of subsistence farmers in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) (Enyiukwu et al., 2014a). Pesticides of plant origin are biodegradable, easy to find, prepare and use in tropical farm settings (Okigbo, 2004; Awurum and Enyiukwu, 2013). This paper therefore, presents a review of indigenous plant species as sources of novel pesticides to combat mycotoxin contamination in stored agricultural products.

Mycotoxigenic fungi and mycotoxins detected in some agricultural products in Afro-Asia

Several surveys indicated the association of different species of *Aspergillus*, *Alternaria*, *Fusarium*, *Rhizopus*, *Penicillium*, *Rhodotorula*, *Heminthoporium*, *Clasporium* etc. with the contamination of polished rice, wheat, bread, tea, and nuts such as peanuts, pistachios and walnuts consumed in Iran (Aghili et al., 2009; Kazemi et al., 2008; 2009; 2013a; 2013b). One such survey on bakers' flour revealed up to 68.5% contamination with mycotoxigenic pathogens (Kazemi et al. 2013a). Similar surveys by Lutfullah and Hussain (2012) in different locations of Pakistan depicted that 30% sorghum and 40% maize consumed in that country were contaminated with aflatoxins, with deposits of up to 13.0µg/kg detected in the maize samples. In Africa and Asia, Kazemi et al. (2014) revealed that *A. niger* and *A. flavus* have been implicated in the toxic deterioration of 30.97 million MT of peanuts and pistachios on annual basis. These fungal contaminants affect produce quality, produce end-products and ultimately food safety (Kazemi et al., 2009). According to these investigators experimental and epidemiological evidences suggested that consumption of foods contaminated with such mycotoxigenic fungi over a long period of time pose important public health risks. For instance, contamination of feedstuff with *A. fumigatus* and *A. flavus* in a trial caused histological changes such as congested nephrons, collapse of glomerulus and aggregation of lymphatic cells in intestinal lamina of laboratory rats (Abad et al., 2013). Such histological abrasions were traceable to mycotoxins produced by the fungal contaminants (Ijei and Obidoa, 2010). Some mycotoxins associated with some agro-commodities in some third world countries of Afro-Asia are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Mycotoxins contamination in some foodstuffs in Afro-Asia.

Country	Commodity	Mycotoxin	Level	Source
Saudi Arabia	Peanuts	Aflatoxins	28 µg/kg	Ostadrahimi et al., 2014
Nigeria	Groundnuts	Aflatoxins	10-176 ppb	Bankole et al., 2005
South Africa	Cowpeas	Fumonisin	0.6-25.30 µg/kg	Kritzing et al., 2003
Iran	Walnuts	Aflatoxins	14.4±8.4 µg/kg	Ostadrahimi et al., 2014
Iran	Peanut (roasted)	Aflatoxins	17.99±18.70 µg/kg	Ostadrahimi et al., 2014
Benin Republic	Cowpea	Aflatoxins	3.52 µg/kg	Houssou et al., 2009
Nigeria	Yam chips	Aflatoxins	4-18 µg/kg	Bankole and Adebajo, 2003
Nigeria	Maize	Aflatoxins	3-138 µg/kg	Bankole and Mabekoje, 2004
Nigeria	Shelled melon	Aflatoxins	5-20 µg/kg	Bankole et al., 2004
Pakistan	Chilli	Aflatoxins	0.1-96.2 µg/kg	Paterson, 2007
Benin	Maize	Fumonisin	3310ng/g	Doko et al., 1995
South Africa	Maize bread	Fumonisin	142-550µg/kg	Lino et al., 2007
Ethiopia	Sorghum	Fumonisin	2117µg/kg	Ayalew et al., 2006
Zambia	Cereals	Fumonisin	1710ng/g	Doko et al., 1995
Egypt	Corn	Ochratoxin A	9.3-15µg/kg	Amra, 2007
Ethiopia	Cereals	Ochratoxin A	5.1-2106µg/kg	Ayalew et al., 2006
Nigeria	Rice	Ochratoxin A	24-116 µg/kg	Makun et al., 2007
Tunisia	Wheat flour	Ochratoxin A	0.0025-10.5 µg/kg	Ayidin et al., 2008
Kenya	Wheat	Zearalenone	1.0-96 µg/kg	Muthomi et al., 2008
Nigeria	Rice	Zearalenone	24-1169 µg/kg	Makun et al., 2007
India	Apple juice	Palutin	21-845 µg/kg	Saxena et al., 2009
South Africa	Apple juice	Palutin	5.0-45 µg/kg	Leggott and Shephard, 2001
China	Corn	Deoxynivanenol	0.256-21 µg/kg	Li et al., 1999

TYPES OF MYCOTOXINS

Aflatoxins

Aflatoxins are polyketide secondary metabolites from toxigenic strains of *Aspergillus* and related species (Da Costa et al., 2010). Chemically they are difuro-coumarins which are freely soluble in chloroform and methanol. They are stable at high temperatures but unstable to UV light or polar solvents (Farg, 2008). This group of mycotoxins are closely related in structure and there are 18 different relatives of aflatoxins, out of which four AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁ and AFG₂ are reported agriculturally common. However, AFB₁ and AFB₂ are the most important and AFB₁ have been adjudged the most toxic (Miller, 1999; Bhat and Vasanthi, 2003; Greekmore, 2012; Da Costa et al., 2010). According to Razzaghi-Abyaney et al., 2010; *Aspergillus flavus*, *Emergella astellata*, *E. venezuelensis* and *A. pseudotamarii* produce AFB₁ and AFB₂ while *A. parasiticus*, *A. nominus*, *A. bombycus*, *A. miniscleotigenes*, *A. arachidicola* produce AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁ and AFG₂ toxins. The toxicity profile of aflatoxins is B₁>M₁>G₁> B₂>M₂.G₂ etc (Farg, 2008). AFB₁ has been reported to contaminate 25% of the global food supply. Aflatoxigenic organisms are common fungi that inhabit the soil and a variety of decaying organic matter as saprophytes (Miller, 1999; Razzaghi-Abyaney et al., 2013). A recent study documented that the distribution of aflatoxin contamination in different agro-ecological zones of Senegal established that the soil is a reservoir for field infections in much the same way as poor storage practices (Tiffany, 2013). *A. flavus* is widespread in both temperate and tropical countries (Greekmore, 2012). *Aspergillus spp.* can attack various commodities including groundnut, maize and spices, vegetables, cocoa, coffee, beer, eggs and meat amongst many others agricultural products. Affected grains may not appear overtly mouldy and producing fungus proliferates in improperly stored grains of moisture content greater than 14%, relative humidity greater than 70%, pH 4-6 and temperature 30-40°C (Greekmore, 2012; Whitlow and Hagler, 2013) Maize is prone to field infections by *Aspergillus*; and the crop debris is reported as the primary source of inocula in the USA. The fungal sclerotia survive many years in the soil, germinate and produce numerous conidia during silking. Soil dwelling mites feed on the germinated sclerotia and thus spread the conidia (Miller, 1999). Contaminations generally are more frequent in tropical zones with inclement weather situations; in such zones replete with poor traditional storage facilities, rice is also prone to aflatoxin contamination (Miller, 1999). Insect damage exacerbates kernel infection in maize grown in the USA. *Aspergillus* ear rot and mouldiness are favoured by hail, drought stress and early frost. However, the amount of aflatoxin deposit in corn is influenced by high temperatures, high grain moisture content (15-18%), pH and nitrogen deficiency (John and Steve, 2010; Tiffany, 2013).

Aflatoxins are heat stable, not eliminated completely by normal cooking procedure (Kishore et al., 2002). They are efficiently absorbed in the small intestine perhaps at the duodenum. The liver is their main target organ but may affect other organs based on their reactivity with DNA, RNA, enzymes and proteins. Mycotoxins undergo metabolism via cytochrome p450 enzymes in the liver. WHO in 2006 reported the presence of AFM₁ in human breast milk in Nigeria and affirmed that children feeding on such breast milk will be stunted and may suffer neurological impairment. Aflatoxin epoxide (8, 9 epoxide) is their major toxic metabolite which binds to DNA or RNA to form adducts. Adducts especially at N7-guanine implicates the compound in carcinogenesis and inducement of hepato-cellular carcinoma (HCC). One such mutation is suspected to occur at human P53 tumor suppression gene at codon 249, leading to the conversion of guanine (G) to thymine (T) at the third nucleotide of the codon (Murphy et al., 2006). In the presence of water, AFB₁-8, 9-dihydrodiol is formed which reacts with serum proteins (lysine or albumin) thus informing the toxicity of aflatoxins (Allameh et al., 2011; Mycotoxin Information, 2013). According to Tiffany (2013) HBV infections are commonly associated with chronic ingestion of aflatoxins. Studies in China authenticated a correlation between aflatoxin B₁ and hepatitis B virus (HBV) in human hepato-cellular carcinoma (Bhat, 2008). Aflatoxin-induced hepatitis outbreaks have been reported in India, Malaysia and Kenya (Bhat and Vasanthi, 2003). In china for example, statistics say that 100,000 patients are diagnosed annually of aflatoxic hepato-cellular carcinoma (HCC); representing 45% of people living with this disease around the world whose mortality rate is estimated at over 95% (Mycotoxin Information, 2013). In 2008, a total of 43,345 cancer related deaths reportedly occurred in SSA (Fapohunda, 2013), with one-third of these deaths due possibly to AFB₁-induced hepatocellular carcinoma (Ijei and Obidoa, 2010).

Besides their synergism with HBV in the etiology of liver cancer; WHO (2006) reported that aflatoxins are suspected to interact with HIV/AIDS. Aflatoxins can also affect domestic animals and fish and their susceptibility is influenced by species, age and diets. For instance birds are more susceptible than mammals (Greekmore 2012). Aflatoxins may cause immune suppression, impair growth and weight gain, damage the liver and lead to death of livestock or man (John and Steve, 2010). Farag (2008) reported that aflatoxins lower resistance to diseases and interfere with vaccine-induced immunity. The mechanism by which this is thought to happen is by the disturbances in protein, carbohydrate and lipid metabolisms. In West Africa where natives eat high maize-based meals, the high reports of incidences of kwashiorkor in the region have been correlated to aflatoxin contamination of their diets (Tiffany, 2013).

In the Republics of Togo and Benin, high concentrations of aflatoxins have been detected in children less than 5 years old weaned on maize-based meals. This source further remarked that in the year 2002 in Kenya, 317 people were reported ill while 125 actually died from consumption of contaminated maize-based meals. Previously 100 out of 400 people died in 1974 from eating such maize-based meals in India (Lawley, 2013). These deaths probably resulted from immune-toxicity in which lymphocytes (T-cell, macrophage, natural killer cell, and B-cells) immune functions were suppressed or perturbed by these toxins (Reddy et al., 2010a). A study on 327 babes in Nigeria reported by Reddy et al. (2010a) underscored aflatoxins for contributing to neonatal jaundice in the infants.

Besides these, aflatoxin contamination causes inferior crop quality and barriers international marketability of produce; especially oil seeds such as groundnut which require stricter lower limits of aflatoxins for exports into the EU and USA (Razzaghi-Abyaney et al., 2010). According to Tiffany (2013), 85% of samples of peanut oil from Senegal contain on the average 40 ppb of AFB₁. Maize samples from Nororo district of the same country showed up to 852.5 ppb while locally produced snack peanuts and feed cakes showed aflatoxin levels of between 25-236 ppb. In 1999, Kishore et al. (2002) reported that an alarming amount of 851.9 µg/kg aflatoxins were detected in peanut samples from Anantapur district of India. And 38% of isolates from 173 samples of the grain lots produced between 44.3-1598 µg/kg aflatoxins in culture studies.

These toxins jeopardize food safety exceeding standards set for food for human consumption and impairing exportability of these commodities into the USA or UAE and EU with maximum allowable total aflatoxin limits of 20 ppb and 4 ppb respectively (Farag, 2008; Allameh et al., 2011; Tiffany, 2013). Consequently, Africa loses 670-750 million USD annually to EU restrictive standard for aflatoxins on cereals, dried fruits and nuts; and billions on the same issue the world over (Okello et al., 2010). Members of the African Groundnut Council put the annual costs of programmes aimed at preventing or reducing aflatoxin contamination at US\$ 7.5 million (Bhat and Vasanthi, 2003). Economic losses however, may reach 100% when the entire product is rejected by the markets (Okello et al., 2010).

Fumonisin

Fumonisin were first isolated from culture studies in South Africa in 1988 (Viljoen, 2013) and are widely reported throughout the continent of Africa today (Okello et al., 2010). As a matter of fact fumonisin have assumed as much toxicological importance as aflatoxins (Bhat, 2008). Chemically they are similar in structure to sphingosine – a component of sphingolipids which are concentrated in myelin and certain nerve tissues of living organisms. Fumonisin B₁, B₂ and B₃ are produced by *Fusarium moniliforme* (*F. verticilloides*), *F. proliferatum*, *F. nygamai* and *Alternaria alternata* f. sp. *lycopersici* (Withlow and Hagler, 2013; Reddy et al., 2010a; Viljoen, 2013). These *Fusarium* pathogens have been implicated in causing fusarium kernel rot of maize and other cereals, a disease associated with dryness and insect damage. Other fumonisin organisms are *F. chlamydosporium*, *F.*

sambucinum, *F. semitectum* and *F. equiseti* (Goswami et al., 2008). *Fusarium verticilloides* has been underscored as cause of seedling blight, stalk rot and ear rot of some cereals (Reddy et al., 2010a). *Fusarium spp.* are widely distributed plant pathogens and known contaminants of stored agricultural products or waste grains (Greekmore, 2010). Hot humid conditions with temperature ranges of 40-65°C is reported to favour fusariotoxin production on grains (Reddy et al., 2010a). In the Kissi district of Kenya, 3600-11,600 ppb fumonisins have been found on maize while 29,000 ppb was documented from maize grains in Burkina Faso (Fapohunda, 2013). According to Bryden (2007), fumonisins are not only associated with maize but also commonly found in maize-based products. In like manner studies showed that *F. equiseti* isolated from ginseng fields attacked a wide range of legumes and cereals such as common bean, bush bean, broad bean, alfalfa, canola and wheat (Goswami et al., 2008). This organism in an evaluation in South Africa produced fumonisin B₁ ranging from 0.12-0.61µg/g on cowpea seeds; with total fumonisins peaking at 25.30µg.g in the study (Kritzinger et al., 2003). Fumonisin organisms attack stressed and senescent crops in the field (Miller, 1999). *Fusaria* and their related species occur systemically in roots, stems, leaves and kernels of susceptible crops and can be recovered from all maize kernels. Studies according to this source suggested that the fungi seem to have a mutualistic association with maize crop producing metabolites of value such as fusaric acid and gibberellins for the plant.

Organisms exposed to fumonisins show pathological changes such as liver or pancreatic necroses, kidneys and liver weight increases, liver damage, increased concentration of haemoglobin, diarrhoea and neurotic effects (Mycotoxin Information, 2013). At low doses fumonisins caused liver and kidney damage in pigs (Miller, 1999). They affect swines, donkeys and mules; and the fatal disease of horses' equine leukoencephalomalacia (ELEM) has been attributed to fumonisins. Fusarial metabolites are hepatotoxic and their cancer promoting activity in rats has been reported. Fumonisin are also possible human carcinogens (Miller, 1999; Withlow and Hagler, 2013). Oesophageal cancer cases in China, Northeast Italy and Transkei Region of South Africa have been reported to be linked to fumonisins (Bhat and Vasanthi, 2003; Reddy et al., 2010a; Withlow and Hagler, 2013). According to John and Steve (2010), up to 10 fumonisins have been identified; however Fumonisin B₁, B₂ and B₃ are commonly of agricultural importance with B₁ reputed as the most toxic. Reddy et al. (2010), noted that intact fumonisins have low bioavailability. Heating such as roasting during food processing noted these authors, converts fumonisins side chains to chemically reactive forms that couple the toxins covalently to amino groups on proteins. Studies have also shown that frying may increase the inherent toxicity of hydrolysed fumonisins by converting them to N-fatty acetyl-hydrolysed fumonisins which have been found 10 times more toxic in culture trials. These toxic metabolites affect sphingolipid synthesis and the biosynthesis of the polyketides (Miller, 1999). Fumonisin toxicity is thought to result from causing electrolyte loss in affected tissues, blockage of sphingolipid synthesis; or disruption of sphingolipid metabolism through inhibition of ceramide synthase activity (Norred, 1993; Miller, 1999; Withlow and Hagler, 2013).

Trichothecenes

Trichothecenes contain 200-300 related compounds produced by certain species of *Fusarium* (Withlow and Hagler, 2013). They are broadly classified into two groups A and B based on their chemistry. Types A (T-2 toxin, HT-2 toxin, DAS) contain ketones at carbon position 8 (C-8). Members of this group are soluble in non-polar solvents. Toxins constituting types B trichothecenes (DON, NIV, Fusarenon X) contain carbonyl at the same carbon position (Mycotoxin Information, 2013). DON (Vomitoxin) is the trichothecene most commonly encountered in the field (Bryden, 2007). It has been reported in maize in South Africa with low incidences in storage (Okello et al., 2010). *Fusarium graminearum*, *F. culmorum* and *F. crookwellence* produce DON, NIV and zearalenone depending on the geographic region of isolate especially in temperate zones. Amongst these *F. graminearum* is the most virulent of these pathogens; affecting maize, wheat, barley and to a lesser extent oat, rye and triticale (Miller, 1999). DON according to this author is widely reported to occur wherever cereals are grown except in upland wheat and in susceptible grains in the colder seasons of the year. Its production in such grains is favoured by high moisture content (>20%) and drying produce to <15% moisture content disfavours the moisture activity of the inciting fungus (Greekmore, 2012; Viljoen, 2013).

DON mostly affects pigs and to a lesser extent poultry. It limits feed consumption in swines being acutely toxic at 1µg/g of their diets. In terms of reproduction this toxin induces such effects as abortions, still births and weak offspring. In poultry, DON is reported to reduce egg quality and weight; in wild birds like Sandhill cranes ulceration of skin and surfaces of their oral cavities are known to occur; while in other domestic animals it causes nausea, diarrhoea, gastrointestinal bleeding and neurologic abnormalities. This fusarial toxin causes facial rash, throat irritation, vomiting and diarrhoea in affected humans. Humans also suffer suppressed immunity following infection with DON making them vulnerable to pathogenic infections. It underscored episodes of gastro-intestinal track distresses which broke out in the Kashmir valley of India in 1987. In 7 states in the USA, DON outbreaks were recorded in 17 schools with affected people presenting nausea, vomiting and abdominal pains. There were no mortalities at the end.

However, DON is not listed as a possible human carcinogen (Miller, 1999; Bhat, 2008; Greekmore, 2012; John and Steve, 2010). Other trichothecenes commonly associated with agricultural commodities are DAS and T-2 toxins. T-2 toxins (*Fusarium sporotrichoides*, *F. poae*) are found in barley, millet and safflower feeds. T-2 is a

potent mycotoxin causing gastro-enteritis, intestinal pile, depression, listlessness, anorexia and hind quarter ataxia in affected animals. Generally, trichothecenes exert their toxicity through protein, DNA, RNA synthesis inhibition at the ribosomal or polysomal levels. They are especially toxic to rapidly dividing cells causing lysis and impeding mitosis. Their toxic site is the 12, 13- epoxytrichothecene ring (Withlow and Hagler, 2013; Mycotoxin Information, 2013).

Zearalenone

Zearalenone (ZER) is a resorcylic acid lactone with no actual toxicity, occurring in both tropical and temperate localities on a variety of cereals (Withlow and Hagler, 2013). It is an oestrogen analogue and causes hyperoestrogenism in farm animals due to its similarity with estradiol the most important female sex hormone. *Fusarium graminearum* the ear rot and stalk rot fungus of cereals is implicated as its major producer. *Fusarium oxysporium* and *F. culmorum* in addition have been reported to produce the toxin ZER (Kishore et al., 2002). According to this source, *Fusarium spp* isolated from 266 samples of groundnut from Anantanpur India in 1999, yielded up to 98.1-847.3µg/kg of zearalenone in culture studies. However, its incidence in storage is reportedly low (Viljoen, 2013). Wet, rainy or humid weather at flowering promotes its infection in susceptible cereals such as wheat, sorghum, barley, rye, sesame and oats. High relative humidity coupled with delayed harvest of produce leads to its accumulation in affected crops. No or minimum tillage has also been reported to increase the amount of fusarium head blight (FHB) in small grains. The toxin is heat-stable, not destroyed by long storage, roasting or by the addition of mould retardants or propionic acid to grains (Viljoen, 2013).

ZER may cause diarrhoea, enlargement of mammary glands, feminization symptoms, impaired semen quality and testicular or ovarian atrophy (Mycotoxin Information, 2013). Pigs and sheep seem more susceptible to this mycotoxin than cattle. Intake from contaminated feedstuff resulted to 10-20% decline in fertility of ewes and reduced twinning rates in other domestic animals (Withlow and Hagler, 2013). This toxin according to Mycotoxin Information (2013) undergoes a two-step transformation; hydroxylation into α - or β -zearalenone catalysed by 3 α - and 3 β hydrosteroid dehydrogenases (HSDs); and conjugation with glucuronic acid catalyzed by uridine diphosphate glucuronyl transferases (UDPGTs). Hydroxylation appears species-specific, pigs convert the compound to α - ZER while cattle to predominantly β - ZER. This is then reduced to zearalenol which has increased estrogenic effect. ZER is rapidly absorbed in the small intestine, complexes to oestrogen receptors and transferred to the nucleus where it binds to specific nuclear receptors mimicking oestrogen. It is not a possible human carcinogen (Miller, 1999).

Ochratoxins

Ochratoxins are naturally occurring mycotoxins soluble in organic solvents, aqueous solution of sodium bicarbonate and slightly soluble in water (Sorrenti et al., 2013). Chemically they consist of isocoumarin moiety linked by a peptide bond to phenylalanine (Mycotoxin Information, 2013). They are produced by *Aspergillus ochraceus*, *A. auricomus*, *A. glaucus*, *A. carbonarius*, *A. alliaceus*, *A. melleus*, *A. niger*, *Penicillium verucosum* and related fungi. *A. niger* plays roles in industrial manufacture of enzymes and citric acid; as such care should be taken that only atoxigenic strains of the fungus is employed in such processes. *Penicillium verucosum* is common to temperate Northern Europe while *A. ochraceus* is pan-tropical in distribution. This group of mycotoxins are entirely actively produced in storage though there are some reports of *P. verucosum* infecting produce between anthesis and harvest (Miller, 1999; Reddy et al., 2010a). Ochratoxins are mainly found associated with cereals but have also been isolated from wines, coffee, spices and dried fruits (Bryden, 2007). Its occurrence on barley is high on a world scale (Reddy et al., 2010a), but common on cocoa in SSA (Fapohunda, 2013). Four ochratoxins have been identified as ochratoxins A, B, C, and D with ochratoxin A (OTA) – a non-ribosomal peptide synthase being the most potent poison. They have been adjudged nephrotoxic and carcinogenic (Fapohunda, 2013). Mycotoxin Information (2013) reported that ochratoxins cause kidney and bladder dysfunction, increased water consumption, blood in urine and faecal samples, liver damage, diarrhoea and suppressed immunity to environmental and microbial stressors as some symptoms presented by organisms affected by OTA.

OTA is efficiently absorbed in the small intestine, and transported via the blood, and accumulates in some organs of the body. Its transfer to milk has been reported in rats, rabbits and humans (Sorrenti et al., 2013). This compound is broken down probably by hydrolysis or enzyme systems to 8 metabolites in the body. Two namely open ring OTA (OP-OA) and OTA hydroquinone (OTHQ) are several times more toxic than the original compound (Sorrenti et al., 2013). Ochratoxigenic metabolites are potent nephrotoxins. OTA has been implicated in Balkan endemic nephropathy (BEN) —a progressive nephritis in populations living along the Dunabe River in Romania, Bulgaria and Yugoslavia (Croatia) (Reddy et al., 2010a). This disease is characterized by a decrease in kidney size or its tubular degeneration. An association between BEN and urinary tract tumours is suspected. Ochratoxins have been reported to damage liver of pigs at low concentrations and to reduce the growth rate of affected organisms. It is classed as a potent carcinogen and suspected a risk factor in testicular cancer. Its carcinogenic and cytotoxic properties stem perhaps from free radical-mediated oxidative cell damage. OTA's mechanism of action hence is thought to be based on impeding enzymes involved in phenylalanine metabolism

by inhibiting the synthesis of phenylalanine-tRNA complex. Or it may interact with enzymes that use phenylalanine as substrate such as phenylalanine hydroxylase which catalyse the irreversible hydroxylation of phenylalanine to tyrosine. It is also believed to inhibit mitochondrial ATP production and to stimulate lipid peroxidation (Reddy et al., 2010a; Sorrenti et al., 2013; Mycotoxin Information 2013).

Associative occurrence and additive effects of mycotoxins

Mycotoxigenic fungus may hardly occur alone and naturally contaminated feeds may contain multiple mycotoxins. *Fusarium moniliforme* which produces the toxic fumonisins and *Aspergillus flavus* recognised for aflatoxins are reported to co-occur in maize (Miller, 1999; Binder et al., 2007). In that case, naturally occurring mycotoxins have been noted to be more toxic than same levels of the toxin obtained from pure laboratory cultures. For example impure aflatoxins produced in naturally infected food or feed substances reduced milk production in affected organisms while equal amounts of pure cultures of the toxic compound did not (Withlow and Hagler, 2013). A possible explanation of this could be the presence of other associative mycotoxins in the naturally contaminated food or feedstuff (Peraica et al., 1999). For instance, *Fusarium* toxins are reported to seldom occur alone without one of DON, DAS, NIV and T-2 toxins (Withlow and Hagler, 2013). A survey of 17,316 feedstuff samples in Asia Oceanic confirmed this by revealing that 38% of the sampled materials showed co-occurrence of two or more mycotoxins. For instance deoxynivalenol-3-glucoside always co-occurred with DON on the average of 12% of all DON contaminations (EMAN, 2013). Besides aflatoxins, *Aspergillus flavus* is known to produce sclerotia which contain the indole alkaloids aflatrem and cyclopiazonic acid whose roles in mycotoxicosis according to Peraica et al. (1999) are as yet not determined. Ochratoxins according to John and Steve (2010) are reported to co-occur with citrinin and napthaquinones such as xanthomegnin and viomellin which are hepatotoxic toxins. These authors emphasized further from a study in Iowa USA, that there is a strong correlation between DON and ZER suggesting that if one mycotoxin is present the other is likely so. This view was supported by Reddy et al. (2010a) that DON and ZER co-existed in assayed naturally infected specimens. The co-existence of mycotoxins was further sustained by Binder et al. (2007) who reported the frequent co-occurrence of AFB₁ and Fumonisin B₁ as well as DON or other trichothecenes and ZER in the same grain. Withlow and Hagler (2013) remarked that fusaric acid interacts with DON to produce and promote the toxicity and symptoms observed from this harmful metabolite in affected organisms.

Management strategies for Mycotoxins

There are many strategies that are adopted to control mycotoxins in foods and feeds. On a broad scale these strategies could be partitioned into preventive and curative strategies. Preventive strategies which aim at preventing the growth of the mycotoxigenic fungi and /or their toxin production are two-fold – pre-harvest and post-harvest strategies. On the other hand curative interventions involve the de-activation of already existing mycotoxins in feed or food (Etop, 2013).

Curative strategies

Irradiation according to Allameh et al. (2011) is an effective means of controlling mycotoxins. It ensures control of moulds, insects and prolongs shelf life of treated vegetables and fruits (Farang, 2008; Arya, 2010). Irradiation controls mycotoxin contamination in a dose-dependent manner. Low doses controls insect pests and delays ripening, medium doses reduce food-borne pathogens while large doses ensure sterilization of produce from harmful microorganisms and their toxins. An evaluation found 5, 10, and 20 kGy gamma rays to effect about 48%, 80% and complete destruction of the mycotoxins on assayed produce respectively (Farang, 2008). In an experiment, 10 kGy gamma ray treatments completely eliminated fungal and bacterial populations in both whole and powdered Ashanti pepper; while 20 kGy dose of the radiation completely destroyed AFB₁ in peanuts, yellow corn, and wheat and cotton seed meal. Plasma systems involving high intensity UV rays (75-102 mW/cm²), and low temperatures could increase ionization by reactive species; completely removing DON, NIV, and AFB₁ after 5 seconds of exposure. Radiolysis of water also yielded highly reactive radicals and these readily attacked aflatoxin B₁.

However, their efficacies notwithstanding, they are expensive technologies and may affect the palatability of treated produce which constitute major disadvantages for their adoption by low-input farmers.

Preventive strategies for managing mycotoxins

According to Bhat and Vasanthi (2003) management of aflatoxins by preventive approaches must be pro-poor, well focused and cost effective. The focus should be on high risk agro-produce, at high risk seasons, in high risk areas; and amongst high risk populations. It should follow the hazard analysis and critical control point (HACCP) principle where from the farmstead way through the harvesting, transportation, and value chains of the produce; a significant reduction in mycotoxin contamination of produce is achieved at every stage. The most effective

strategies for managing mycotoxins have been reported to begin with preventive strategies (Tiffany, 2013). The soil being the source of all infections, therefore good management of mycotoxins begins from the farmstead.

PRE-HARVEST CONTROL AND MANAGEMENT

Good agronomic practices (GAPs)

Reddy et al. (2011) remarked that management of mycotoxins through pre-harvest control methods remains imperative and the best approach at initiating their control. According to Bryden (2007) pre-harvest stress factors such as drought and insect infestations make crops to succumb easily to fungal invasion. This author maintained that GAPs which aim at improving the crop vigour, and breeding to improve genetic resistance of field crops to mycotoxigenic fungal attacks, contribute in large measures in reducing the mycotoxin contamination of produce. GAPs include use of resistant cultivars of a given crop wherever available, crop rotation, clean tillage, in addition to seed and/or soil health which help to reduce the amount of fungal inocula available against the crop. Others are adjusting time of planting to make for crop maturation and harvesting not to coincide with peak rains regime, adjusting plant populations for improved air circulation in the field, judicious use of insecticides, proper fertilization of crops to boost their vitality and vigour; and weeding to eliminate alternate host phenomena, competition for nutrient, insolation and space and many such practices targeted at improving crop vigour and performance (Bhat and Vasanthi, 2003; Bhat, 2008). Several GAP practices have been enumerated and reviewed by Bankole and Adebajo (2003) and Enyiukwu et al. (2014a). However, GAP has only modest impact on the control of mycotoxigenic fungi and mycotoxins in the event of epidemics (Miller, 1999). Therefore other strategies have to be incorporated with them in Integrated Disease Management systems to achieve sufficient reduction of mycotoxins to acceptable legal limits in agricultural produce.

POST-HARVEST CONTROL AND MANAGEMENT

Proper harvesting, handling, and storage of produce

Significant levels of grain mould infection begin from the field being encouraged by damp conditions at the time of harvesting, delayed harvesting and continue in storage due to improper or insufficient drying, insect infestation and poor storage conditions of stored produce (Reddy et al., 2013; Tiffany et al. 2013). Proper harvesting and handling of agro-produce are good starting points of post-harvest control of mycotoxins in produce. This is because such practices minimize abrasions and breakages of produce which provide portals of entry for mycotoxigenic fungi. According to the WHO (2006) good postharvest practices are directed to achieving minimization of mycotoxin contamination through proper drying and storage techniques as well as elimination of undue moisture migration into produce during storage or marketing. In many traditional storage systems of Senegal Tiffany (2013) reported that storage is done in bins, rooms and roomlets. In such systems aflatoxin contamination has been reported. In many third world economies, WHO (2006) noted that the combination of insufficient drying and humid atmospheric conditions warranted unacceptable levels of mycotoxins on harvested maize, groundnut etc. The parameters of moisture and temperature are known to influence to a large degree the activities of fungi (Bryden, 2007), with moisture regarded as the single most important determinant of how rapidly mycotoxigenic moulds grow in storage (Whitlow and Hagler, 2013).

Therefore, ensuring that harvester combines are set properly to reduce breakage of kernels; and that produce are sorted and winnowed properly to remove bruised and broken tubers or kernels which could become easily infected in the store will go a long way to reduce or remove contamination in produce (WHO, 2006; Tiffany, 2013). To this end therefore, we should dry grains always to safe moisture content (13-14%) before storing. Usually drying should be done on covered surfaces not on bare grounds as this will increase the propensity of mycotoxin contamination. And store only clean grains in insecticide-treated bags on racks in a properly maintained, fumigated and ventilated store-house; and ensure that produce are dried to safe moisture levels before storing. It is important that old crops are evacuated before introducing new ones and that stored produce are stored only for minimal possible time periods (Bhat, 2008; John and Steve, 2010). These simple postharvest technologies in subsistence farm levels of west Africa have been found to reduce disease burdens due to aflatoxins as reported by WHO (2006). The essence of good store structure, condition and hygiene is not only to reduce fungal load on grains but to minimize insect and moisture migration into the bin which could stimulate and ultimately quicken the growth and sporulation of the storage fungi. Good store conditions and hygiene have been reviewed by Bankole and Adebajo (2003) and Enyiukwu et al. (2014a).

Cottage technologies for value addition to agro-produce

One of the most important factors affecting most African countries in their quest for food security is lack of cottage industries through which they could add time and utility values to agro-produce. Many of the mycotoxin-

prone foods are staples from cereals and tubers or oil seeds. It is a known fact that bruised or broken kernels of cereals or tubers may easily get infected by mycotoxigenic fungi. Such broken kernels from improperly set harvester combines could be used immediately to produce other high value products such as chips, flakes, powders and flours. Similarly tubers could be used to produce scientific grade gins and spirits to drive small machines and automobiles. In this way much wastage will be curtailed as what could not be stored for long periods of time could be converted to other forms of products that store longer and are less mycotoxin-prone (Okello et al., 2010; Enyiukwu et al., 2014a).

Legislative and phyto-sanitary enforcement

In several developed economies of the world such as USA, Europe and some parts of Asia, the maximum allowed limits for total mycotoxins are prescribed for food and industrially manufactured products. Up to 77 countries of the world have regulations addressing mycotoxins (FAO, 2004). Viljoen (2013) reported that proper legislative policies, competent capacities and accurate detection and diagnostics underpin good management of fungi-generated toxins. According to Tiffany (2013) the US Department of Agriculture (USDA) play significant roles in preventing mycotoxin contaminated crops and products from reaching the consumer markets through the twin pillars of phytosanitary standards enforcement and mycotoxin detection technologies. To do this effectively the toxins must be detected promptly in samples or specimens.

Blacklight technology based on the use of UV light to detect fluorescence produced from kojic acid in mycotoxigenic pathogens. usually used for the detection of mycotoxins (especially aflatoxins) is only presumptive. This technology though relatively cheap, is however disadvantaged because of high false positive and negative results it gives. On the other hand, serological technologies (detection kits) that are fairly quick, inexpensive, and easy to perform which rely on antibodies that selectively capture a specific mycotoxin that has been extracted from an ingredient, are available now for mycotoxin detection (Herman and Trigo-Stockli, 2002). Some of the commercially available kits are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Some commercially available test kits for mycotoxins

Mycotoxins											
Aflatoxins	Det. level (ppb)	DON	Det. level (ppm)	T-2 Toxin	Det. level (ppm)	ZER	Det.level (ppm)	OTA	Det. level (ppm)	Fum.	Det. level (ppm)
Aflatest*	1	Agriscreen	2.0	Veratox	0.15	Veratest	0.1	Veratox	0.01	Veratox	1-6
Agriscreen*	5	Myctest*	0.5	EZScreen	0.05	EZScreen	0,1	EZScreen	0.02	Fumonitest*	5-100
Aflacup 10	10	Veratox*	0.5	Mycotest*	0.25	Mycotest*	0.5	Ochratest*	0.05-		
Aflacup 20	20					Zearalatest	0.2-100		1.0		
EZ-Screen	20										

Source: Herman and Trigo-Stokli, 2002. * kit gives quantitative detection. Det. = detectable.

However, reliable and appreciable quantitative detection of these toxins requires very sophisticated and expensive laboratory equipment and skilled analytical chemists (Bryden, 2007). Conventionally mycotoxins such as aflatoxins, ochratoxins, DON, ZER, T-2 and fumonisins are detected in such laboratory assays through thin layer chromatography (TLC), high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), gas liquid chromatography (GLC), and spectrometry. Mycotoxins remarked Bryden (2007) are known to conjugate to proteins and polyketides making it possible to elicit them or their broken-down products by enzyme linked immune-absorbent assays (ELISA). However, Elbert et al. (2010) noted that modern inexpensive LC-MS/MS simultaneous method of analyses that can detect 9 mycotoxins in a single run has been developed for barley, rye, wheat, and oats. In addition to this, proper and widespread directed awareness campaigns through the electronic or print media as well as proper labelling of products on the agro-production systems adopted for their production have been noted to aid informing consumers of the contents and dangers of products which they choose to eat (Bankole and Adebajo, 2003).

Dietary modification

Reliance on a single crop especially cereals such as maize by natives in Africa as well as insufficient foods in both quantity and quality have been advanced as some of the factors which impair food security in the continent (Adebayo et al., 2010; Kana et al., 2012) and predispose the natives to attacks from mycotoxins (Bryden, 2007). Individuals should endeavour to change diets to avoid risky foods such as maize (Bhat and Vasanthi, 2003) to less risky ones such as millet and sorghum (Bandyopadhyay et al., 2007). The chronic incidence of aflatoxins from such aflatoxin-prone diets is evident from the presence of AFM₁ in umbilical cords of neonates and human breast milk of nursing mothers in Thailand, UAE, Sudan, Sierra Leone, Ghana and Nigeria. Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) generated by metabolism of aflatoxins by liver enzymes results in oxidative stresses due to increased lipid peroxidation and decreased enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidation in the system (Anokwuru

et al., 2011). Metabolism of aflatoxin B₁ yields aflatoxin 8, 9-epoxide which readily binds to cellular macromolecules, proteins and DNA to form adducts. Adducting with N7- guanine for example, results in gene mutations and cancer. Inhibition of aflatoxin 8,9-epoxide (AFBO) formation through disruption of cytochrome P450 system and/or adduct formation is considered as important strategies for preventing the damaging mutations. Kolaviron afforded by *Garcinia kola* significantly prevented AFB₁-induced liver toxicity in a trial by scavenging reactive intermediates produced by conjugation with glutathione or glucuronic acid (Farombi, 2003). Neem (*Azadirachta indica* L.) as constituent of medicines or food additives enhanced hepatic glutathione and glutathione-dependent enzymes; and as such played significant roles in ameliorating mycotoxins impacts in the body (Anokwuru et al., 2011).

Addition of nutrients or additives is advanced as another effective approach to prevent dangerous adducts formation. Sorrenti et al. (2013) noted that α -tocopherol, phenolic compounds, lycopene and zinc ameliorated OTA-induced retardation in cell viability by efficiently reducing reactive oxygen species (ROS) production. They hence confirmed the effectiveness of dietary strategies in overcoming the OTA toxicity. Research indicated that vitamins A, C and riboflavin are capable of preventing the binding to and disallowing formation of aflatoxin B₁-DNA adduct. Similar report also revealed that sulphur-rich amino acids inhibited AFB₁-stimulated mutagenicity in microbial systems (Farag, 2008).

It is thought for example that antioxidants are able to counteract the deleterious effects of chronic consumption or exposure to ochratoxin A. Experiments as continued by Farag (2008) revealed that essential oils (EOs) from nutmeg, celery, black pepper, cardamon with antioxidant activity disallowed aflatoxin B₁-DNA bonding. Some heavy metals such as copper, zinc, manganese and selenium inhibited mycotoxin-dependent mutagenicity. Perhaps, they achieved these feats by antioxidant activity. Therefore, fortifying or modifying feeds or industrially produced foods with these nutrients, vitamins or essential oils will possibly reduce the harmful effects of mycotoxins in the food chain. Greater than 99% of the populations of many areas of West Africa are reported positive to long-term aflatoxin exposures. A recent study in Nigeria found that maize was more heavily colonised by aflatoxigenic strains of *Aspergillus spp.* than either sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*), and millet (*Pennisetum glaucus*) with its overall aflatoxin levels being correspondingly higher (Bandyopadhyay et al., 2007). The authors hence recommended a shift from maize cultivation and consumption to millet or sorghum which is indigenous and less mycotoxin-prone. Eating diets based on cereals such as maize and oilseeds such as groundnuts should be downplayed in favour of vegetable or fruit-rich diets capable of furnishing the body with the requisite vitamins, EOs or minerals to combat mycotoxin damage in tissues.

Biological control of mycotoxins

Initially it was thought that mycotoxin contamination was solely a storage problem, it has been found to a large extent that the field is the primary source of this contamination. On-farm trials revealed that bio-control agents could be helpful in deterring mycotoxigenic fungi. According to Peraica et al. (1999) in an experiment, the use of spores of non-toxigenic strain of *Aspergillus flavus* isolated from Western farms has greatly reduced aflatoxin levels in cotton seeds. In a recent evaluation, conducted on maize farms in Nigeria, atoxigenic isolates of *A. flavus* (Aflasafe®) significantly controlled aflatoxin contamination with 80-90% success recorded from the trials (Fapohunda, 2013; Tiffany, 2013). Available data have shown that lactic acid bacteria inhibit mould growth and can potentially impede mycotoxin production (Dalie et al., 2010). Reddy et al. (2010b) found culture filtrates of *Rhodococcus erythropolis*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens* and *Trichoderma viride* to vehemently retard *Aspergillus flavus* growth and impede AFB₁ production from them. In some studies conducted *in vivo* a bacterium *Eubacterium sp.* was found to strongly detoxify trichotecenes; while yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) cell wall-derived glucomannan could bind and lock both aflatoxins and fumonisins in feeds effectively. According to Alameh et al. (2010) *Rhodococcus erythropolis* and *Mycobacter flouranthenivorans* completely eliminated all traces of aflatoxins within 24 h in a trial. It is considered that peptidoglycans or polysaccharides play roles in these activities. For instance *Favobacterium aurantiacum* and *Enteococcus faecium* have peptidoglycans in their cell wall components which bind and absorb aflatoxins (Alameh et al., 2010). Others such as atoxigenic strains of *Rhizopus sp.*, *Phoma sp.*, *Trichoderma sp.* and *Alternaria sp.* produce large secretions of extracellular enzymes which have been implicated in degrading AFB₁. Though the mechanisms of action of these bio-control agents have not been fully explained, competition for space and nutrients, antibiosis, direct parasitism; as well as rapid and effective colonization of wound sites against the invading pathogens have been presumed and suggested for their activity against mycotoxigenic mycoflora (Enyiukwu et al., 2014a). Knowledge of genomics and proteomics is postulated may give adequate understanding to gene functions including tissue invasion by pathogens, pesticide resistance, and genes supporting mycotoxin synthesis. It is suggested that bioinformatics softwares such as e-fungi, CFGP, SNUGB, PLATCOM, FUNGI path etc. could enable scientists to compare genomes of mycotoxigenic fungi towards understanding the ones involved in toxin synthesis and how to mitigate them, in order to enhance bio-control (Kazemi, 2011; 2013). However, as novel and feasible as these strategies could be, they may not be economically viable in the hunger prone and high risk regions of third world countries (Bryden, 2007) and formulating and presenting bio-agents in such a way that low-input farmers making up the large numbers of growers of different crops subsistentially; in the country can apply them is still elusive.

Chemical control

Control of rots in agricultural produce have been attempted with significant benefits with bleach (sodium hypochlorite), borax, captan, orthio-phenylphenate, naphthalene acetic acid, maleic hydrazidine, lime and gin (Okigbo, 2004; Okigbo and Nmeke, 2005). For example the protectant fungicide captan was found to completely inhibit the germination of spores of the rot-inducing organisms; *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Botrydipodia theobromae* and *Penicillium sclerotigenum* while benlate and thiobendazole arrested both spore germination as well as growth of these pathogenic species. Many chemical agents such as ammonia, propionic acid and some additives have been evaluated against rots causing organisms (Enyiukwu et al., 2014a) and mycotoxin contamination in silages (Whitlow and Hagler, 2013). Chlorophyllin and oltipraz could reduce exposure to mycotoxins (Bhat and Vasanthi, 2003; Bhat, 2008). Calcium and sodium bisulphide are also known chemicals for mycotoxin control (Alameh et al., 2011). This source added that sodium bisulphide chelates with double bond of the furo-furan ring of aflatoxin forming AFB₁-sulphorate, thus disallowing the ring from reacting with DNA. According to Banu and Johnpaul (2010) ammonia gas fumigation reduced both infections by *A. flavus* on produce and aflatoxin production from the pathogen. Ozone is a strong disinfectant. It attacks the furo-furan ring of mycotoxins through electrophilic activity forming primary ozonoides followed by monozonoides (Allameh et al., 2011). Studies in Pakistan have shown that propionic acid (0.1-0.5%), copper sulphate (0.5-1.0%) and benzoic acid (0.1-0.5%) completely inhibited *A. flavus* and *A. parasiticus* growth (Hussain et al., 2012). A trial with Diocatin A (Dot A) a metabolite from *Streptomyces spp.* as reported by Yoshinari et al. (2007) strongly inhibited production of aflatoxins in *A. parasiticus*. The compound also impeded conidiation of the fungus but could not arrest its mycelia elaboration. Dot A's mechanism of action lies in inhibiting the production of norsolorinic acid (a biosynthetic intermediate of AFB₁) and strongly reducing the mRNA involved in encoding a key regulatory protein for aflatoxin biosynthesis. Earlier investigation by Lotlikar et al. (1989) established that Phenobarbital treatments in experimental rats prevented binding of AFB₁ to DNA in liver cells of the animal. This may have been due to inactivation of reactive AFB₁-epoxide. Synthetic fungicides may promote reactive oxygen species which causes oxidative diseases that damage proteins, lipids, nucleic acids and vitamins (Whitlow and Hagler, 2013). In addition, this source noted that fungicides may reduce mould growth in the field; however the stress and shock from the intervention could trigger the pathogens for increased mycotoxin production. According to Okello et al. (2010) in Kenya, effective fungicides against mycotoxins contamination for groundnuts production have meanwhile not been available. So far fungicides have shown little efficacy in controlling pre-harvest aflatoxin contamination in corn concluded Whitlow and Hagler (2013).

Besides these, the fear of mammalian toxicity and other obvious risks associated with synthetic chemicals resulting from fungicides residues in crops such as allergies and immune dysfunction have heightened consumer concerns for treated food safety. For instance the broad-spectrum biocides captan had been banned in the USA and Europe on grounds of mammalian toxicity (Enyiukwu and Awurum, 2013). All these consequently led to the search for alternatives with minimal risks (Awurum and Enyiukwu, 2013). Such novel alternative approaches according to Allameh et al. (2011) should be easy to use, inexpensive, and not lead to the formation of other compounds that are still toxic, or revert to re-form the parent mycotoxin, or other harmful forms of the compound, or alter the nutritional and/or organo-leptic properties of the treated produce. One alternative that is rapidly gaining grounds in plant health management is user-accessible plant-derived fungicides for the control of toxins in crops (Fapohunda, 2013; Enyiukwu et al., 2014a). These natural products are easily available around farmsteads, easy to prepare and use, less harmful to non-target wildlife and soil edaphons.

Use of plant-based fungicides for the control of mycotoxigenic fungi and mycotoxins

Papachan et al. (2007) indicated that several oriental and tropical plants have been reported to be used for appetite promotion, medicinal purposes and food preservation. The factor underpinning these usages is secondary metabolites (Enyiukwu and Awurum, 2013). Phyto-chemicals as food protectants according to Enyiukwu et al. (2014a) unlike synthetic fungicides leave no toxic load on treated produce, require no pre-harvest interval (PHI) limitation; and contain many bioactive metabolites; an advantage which makes pathogens' development of resistance to them less likely. Several workers have affirmed their efficacy for managing field and storage disease of produce (Awurum et al., 2005; Amadioha, 2012; Awurum and Ucheagwu, 2013). In traditional homesteads of Benin Republic Adjou et al. (2012) reported that leaves of *Ageratum conyzoides* serve as preservatives being introduced into cowpea or maize storage bins to repel insects and disallow storage fungi. Steam-derived essential oil from *Tagetes patula* showed good antifungal activity against *Botrytis cinerea* and *Penicillium digitatum* (Abad et al., 2007). According to Razzaghi-Abyaneh et al. (2010) essential oils from *A. conyzoides* damaged plasma and mitochondria membranes leading to impairing acetylCoA molecules necessary for early steps of aflatoxin biosynthesis form β -oxidation of short chain fatty acids inside the mitochondria. The search for natural sources for novel chemo-inhibitors of aflatoxin biosynthesis this source maintained, has been a subject of intense study and a variety of aflatoxin inhibiting compounds have been reported from medicinal plants.

In an evaluation Hussain et al. (2012) found clove, clove oil, and *Allium spp.* (garlic and onion) to completely inhibit the growth of *Aspergillus flavus* and *A. parasiticus in vitro*. In the Camerouns, Tagne et al.

(2008) showed that extracts and essential oils from *Ocimum gratissimum*, *Cymbopogon citrates* and *Thymus vulgaris* retarded the development of *Fusarium verticilloides* in maize both on-farm and in culture studies. A study in Thailand according to Thanaboripat (2011) revealed that betel vine leaf completely inhibited growth and aflatoxin production of *A. flavus* while tobacco extracts (<10% w/v) significantly inhibited the fungus in culture. Neem-derived azadirachtin a norterpeneoid is a well known aflatoxin inhibitor (Allameh et al., 2011). Neem oil (0.5-4.0% v/v) in a trial as noted by Da Costa et al. (2010) resulted in 95% inhibition of aflatoxin B₁ and B₂ *in vitro* but failed to suppress the fungal growth. This oil remarked (Razzaghi-Abyaney et al., 2010) contained many non-volatile compounds that affected the synthesis of enzymes involved in the early steps of aflatoxin biosynthesis pathway. Coffee leaves and fruits rich in caffeine alkaloids showed antifungal activity against species of *Penicillium* and *Aspergillus* and blocked aflatoxin production from them. This action was linked to inhibition of respiratory systems of the fungus or their glucose uptake necessary for production of acetylCoA. Aqueous extracts of *Zingiber officinale* and leaf extracts of *Trignoella faenum-graecum* inhibited aflatoxin production to significant levels while solvent extracts of *Oxalis corniculata* and *Z. officinales* inhibited both growth and aflatoxin production by *A. flavus* (Reddy et al., 2011).

Oil of *Nigella sativum* (1-3%) completely inhibited aflatoxin production while fruit extract of baobab (*A. digitatum*) inhibited total aflatoxin production by *A. parasiticus* by 69.1% (El-Nagerabi et al., 2013). *Citrus* oil (D-limonene) and essential oils from *Thymus eriocalyx* were found both as fungicidal agent and aflatoxin inhibitors. *Zataria multiflora* rich in carvicrol also prevented the growth and aflatoxin production and synthesis of by toxigenic *Aspergillus* spp. (Allameh et al., 2011). Abad et al. (2007) reported that Polygodial (a sesquiterpene) isolated from *polygonium punctatum* exhibited fungicidal activity against food spoilage yeast *Zygosaccharomyces bailii*. A time kill curve from the study showed that all growth stages of the fungus were affected by the phyto-pesticide. These authors noted further that *Datura metel* L. afforded a novel alkaloidal compound 2-(3, 4-dimethyl-2,5-dihydro-1H-pyrrol-2-yl)-1-methylethyl pentanoate which demonstrated strong antifungal activity against mycotoxigenic *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *A. flavus* and *A. niger*. The hydroxycoumarin scopoletin isolated from *Melia azedarach* also effectively checked advancement of toxigenic *Fusarium verticilloides* (*F. moniliforme*) in culture.

Leaves of *Blumea balsamifera* afforded a flavonoid luteolin which showed moderate antifungal activity against *A. niger* while trifolin from *Camptotheca acuminata* effectively impeded *Alternaria alternata* and *Fusarium avenaceum* *in vitro* (Abad et al., 2007). According to Onuegbu (1999) *vernonia amygdalina* afforded 7, 24(28)-Stimasdie-3-beta-ol which retarded the growth and development of *Aspergillus flavus* and *A. niger* in mung bean (*Vigna radiata* L.). Ijeih and Obidoa (2010) found from *in vivo* studies with rats exposed to AFB₁ and fed diets incorporated with *V. amygdalina* leaves, that the extract protected the liver of the animals from attacks from aflatoxin B₁. Similarly, corroborative study indicated that ethanolic neem extracts at low doses also ameliorated hepatotoxicity and hematological damage induced by dietary aflatoxin in laboratory mice (Anokwuru et al., 2011). This hepato-protective activity of *V. amygdalina* may be due to presence and antioxidant activity of the stimastiol in the extract (Onuegbu, 1999; Da Costa et al., 2010). Aqueous seed extracts from *Carica papaya* is rich in the alkaloid carpaine. This compound significantly impeded the development of rot on pawpaw fruit caused by species of *Aspergillus* (Nwinyi and Abikoye, 2010). Carpaine has high antioxidant activity, an attribute which has been reported responsible for its anti-mycotoxigenic action.

Mode of action of plant-derived aflatoxin inhibitors

Many pathways have been advanced by several sources as possible mechanisms by which phyto-pesticides effect antifungal, anti-aflatoxigenic activities (Allameh et al., 2011). These are denaturation or interference with the enzymes or amino acids for spore germination; damaging of enzyme systems of fungi particularly those involved in energy production and irreversible impairment of cell wall, cell membrane or cellular organelles (Enyiukwu and Awurum, 2013).

Several fractions of plant extracts such as phenylpropanoids, terpenoids and alkaloids have been shown to exhibit anti-aflatoxigenic activities (Razzaghi-Abyaney et al., 2010). The biological activity of an essential oil for instance is related to the presence of secondary bioactive compounds, their proportion of presence and interactions between the different constituting compounds of the oil or extract. *Rosemarinus officinalis*' anti-aflatoxigenic activity is assigned to borneol and pinene in the terpene fraction of the plant materials. Essential oil components may have synergistic and potentiating influences since whole oils may have greater antifungal activity than individual fractions of the oil. Aflatoxin inhibiting properties of phyto-pesticidal agents like eugenol, tannins and some plant components appears according to Allameh et al. (2011) to be due to their antioxidant capabilities. They seem to be cell wall and membrane antagonists (Da Costa et al., 2010). These metabolites contain several functional groups such as phenolic and hydroxyl groups which are very reactive and can easily form bonds with sites on the mycotoxins or their target enzymes to their displacement (Rasooli et al., 2009; Allameh et al., 2011). Though their mechanism of action is not thoroughly understood yet (Gurjar et al. 2012; Enyiukwu et al., 2014b), plant-derived pesticides are suggested to exhibit anti-mycotoxigenic action by interference with enzymatic reaction linked to bioactivation or conjugation of mycotoxins.

CONCLUSION

Mycotoxins are potent but unappreciated silent killers endemic in most tropical countries where large percentages of agro-production are done on subsistence bases. In such low-input, poor storage systems contaminations with toxins from a variety of mycolora is unavoidable, leading to unacceptable levels of mycotoxins in food products. However, efforts should be made at reducing them at every stage of the production-value chain lines; a principle recognized as hazard analyses and critical control points (HACCP). Avoidance of grain damage, prompt and proper drying, as well as proper storage of produce should be emphasized; alongside other pro-poor, well focused and cost effective strategies like phyto-chemical interventions in the tropics. The challenges of power in the third world countries, makes phyto-chemicals veritable sources of fungicides for post-harvest prevention and management of mycotoxin contamination. Given the efficacy of plant-based pesticides in arresting rots, disallowing production of mycotoxins on produce postharvest, and preventing the toxins from binding to hepatic systems of assayed animals *in vivo*; they remain therefore our invaluable tools of defence at combating these toxins with sustainable comparative and competitive advantages in sub-Saharan Africa. Effective extracts powder-formulations should therefore, be used by low-input farmers in tropical farmsteads to preserve agro-produce from rots and mycotoxin contamination.

Suggestions

1. In view of the effectiveness of plant-derived pesticides for postharvest rot and mycotoxin controls, in highly efficacious extracts; detailed screening and study of the plant species for bioactive anti-mycotoxigenic substances are urgently warranted. Aromatic terpene fractions and other medicinal constituents should be isolated and characterised for use as possible alternative or complementary post-harvest antifungal preservatives for commercial uses.
2. Breeding is still one primary means of solving agro-based challenges. It should include broad-range of stresses of all kinds. Organisms such as nuttallid beetles which feed generously on mouldy ears of cereals and are resistant to mycotoxicosis should be studied carefully. Resistance genes in this organism should be identified, mapped and genetically engineered into susceptible crops by transgenic transfers. This will go a long way in solving the problem of mycotoxin contamination in mycotoxin-prone staples such as maize and other cereals.
3. Plants produce allelo-chemicals that interfere with toxin formation. Such chemical has been found in maize against DON and ZER and breeding programs should aim at magnifying the quantity and effects of such chemicals in cereals. Staple crops such as maize, wheat sorghum and millet should also be modified or strengthened with genetic ability to synthesize secondary metabolites identified as efficacious against mycotoxigenic pathogens and mycotoxins from other higher plants through carefully mapped out genetic modification programmes.
4. Studies on the interactive and associative effects of mycotoxins with one another or other synthetic pesticides *in vivo* are strongly warranted and should be pursued vigorously. So also the impacts of farming systems especially organic farming on mycotoxigenic fungal development and contamination of agro-produce.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We are profoundly grateful to Dr. Kazemi Abdolhassan of the Liver and Gastrointestinal Diseases Center, Tabriz University of Medical Sciences IR Iran, for availing us numerous and useful e-materials on surveys conducted on mycotoxigenic fungal contaminants of major staples consumed in Iran.

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Cite this Article: Enyiukwu DN, Awurum AN, Nwaneri JA, 2014. Mycotoxins in Stored Agricultural Products: Implications to Food Safety and Health and Prospects of Plant-derived Pesticides as Novel Approach to their Management: Greener Journal of Microbiology and Antimicrobials, 2 (3): 032-048.